

WORKING CAPITAL MANAGEMENT AND FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE NEXUS: EVIDENCE FROM AFRICAN MANUFACTURING COMPANIES

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Abstracts

The study examined the effect of working capital management on the financial performance of listed manufacturing companies in selected African countries for the period of years 2014–2019. The selected countries are Botswana, Ghana, Kenya, Nigeria, South Africa and Zambia. Nine, thirteen, nineteen, fifty-eight, nine and ten were selected for Botswana, Ghana, Kenya, Nigeria, South Africa and Zambia respectively. The study used secondary data which was analyzed with the use of descriptive and regression analysis (panel fully modified ordinary least square methods). The finding shows that working capital management (WCM) practice varies across selected countries. It also discovered that account receivables period had positive effect with return on equity (ROE) in Botswana and Nigeria while it has positive effect on ROE in Ghana, Kenya, South Africa and Zambia. Account payment period has positive effect in five out of six selected African countries on ROE expect for South Africa which has negative. Inventory management has negative effect in four of the six selected African countries on ROE expect for Kenya and Zambia which has negative effect. Cash conversion cycle has positive effect in five out of six selected African countries on ROE expect for Nigeria which has negative effect. The paper recommended that emphasis should to be placed on the particular component of working capital (that is cash conversion cycle, inventory management, account receivables period and account payment period) as it effects on financial performance measured with ROE in respective countries.

Keywords: Account Receivables Period; Account Payment Period; Inventory Management; Cash Conversion Cycle; Return on equity

1. INTRODUCTION

Working capital (WC) is an important factor to consider when making any financial decision, particularly when it comes to dividend payments, investing, and project funding (Samuel & Fidelis, 2015; Javid, 2014). This is because it has a direct influence on firms' liquidity and profitability as they form a constituent part of the investment (Odunayo, Mishelle & Titilayo, 2017). Decisions on liquidity and profitability are difficult to make while running a company's day-to-day operations. Affordable liquidity ensures that businesses can fulfil their short-term obligations, and a lucrative endeavour can ensure that their cash flow continues (Odunayo et al., 2017). Businesses must be able to run efficiently and financially in order to achieve this. Because of the pressures of smaller credit limits and rising interest rates, demand for enterprises' products and services drops quickly (Akinyemi, 2014). Managers in organizations

face a conundrum in attaining the necessary trade-off between liquidity and profitability in order to optimize a firm's worth (Adeleke & Mukolu, 2013; Padachi, 2006).

The purpose of ensuring effective management of WC is to ensure a balance between the reduction of illiquidity and the avoidance of excess asset composition (Ogundipe, Idowu and Ogundipe, 2012; Eljelly, 2004). A firm will maximize its revenue by increasing its free flow through optimal WC (Aktas, 2015; Ganesan, 2007). Multiple external and internal elements influence a company's performance. It is useful to note that external circumstances affect a company in a variety of ways and are beyond its control. Government norms and regulations, market preferences and perceptions, and the country's economy are all examples. The corporate governance procedures of the company, ownership structure, and risk management of the firm, capital structure of the firm, and the firm's features and policies are all internal elements that may impact the company's success. A company's success is influenced by a variety of external and internal factors. To note that external factors have a range of effects on a firm. Examples of external factors include government standards and laws, market preferences and views, and the country's economy. The company's corporate governance processes, ownership structure, risk management, capital structure, and features and policies are all internal components that may have an influence on the company's performance.

Previous studies have considered component of working capital management on performance but to best of our knowledge, non-have considered commonwealth countries and also long run implication of macroeconomic variable effect on the performance (Asaleye et al., 2022b; Obadiaru et al., 2018). This study examined the long run effect of working capital management component and its effect on performance in African countries within the common wealth nation.

This paper is structured as follows; Section 1 is the introductory, Section 2 discusses the review of literature. Sections 3 and 4 present method of analysis and result respectively. And the study is concluded with Section 5.

2. REVIEW OF EMPIRICAL LITERATURE

Working capital management is the management of both current assets and current liabilities (Olowe, 2008). Current assets and current liabilities include mainly cash, debtors, stock, and creditors. Traditionally, according to Tauringana and Afrifa (2013), investors, bankers, and creditors consider working capital the major element to focus on in the financial statement. The financial health of any company is based on the efficient utilization of working capital management. Working capital is the difference between current assets and current liabilities. Excessive working capital indicates that current assets exceed current liabilities, while low working capital indicates that current assets are less than current liabilities. Efficient working capital management involves proper management of current assets and current liabilities, which makes the business healthy (Nwankwo & Osho, 2010).

The actions and investment decisions of a company's organizations determine its performance. High financial performance indicates that the company's resources are being used effectively and efficiently (Naser & Mokhtar, 2004). The repatriation of assets will be the subject of this

research. The earnings earned by shareholders' equity over a one-year period are referred to as this. If ROE is correctly understood, it may be a powerful tool in the investor's armoury. It includes the three key levers that management may use to safeguard the organization's health: profitability, asset management, and financial leverage. The individuals who own a firm and everyone else who has an interest in it, such as managers, banks, creditors, family members, and workers, are all covered by agency theory. According to the agency theory, the day-to-day operations of a business are carried out by managers who have been hired as agents by the owners of the firm, who are also known as shareholders. In the history of management theory, the resource-based concept has become one of the most prominent and quoted ideas. It aims to explain the internal sources of a company's competitive advantage over time (Kraaijenbrink et al., 2010). Penrose was the one who laid the groundwork for the resource-based perspective as a theory (Roos & Roos, 1997).

Empirically, Lamptey, Frimpong and Morrison (2017) report that there is a negative correlation between the Cash Conversion Cycle, Account Receivable Period, and Inventory Management and the performance of SMEs in Ghana. The study does not consider cross country, and factors that affect the performance of SMEs, such as government policy, infrastructure, among others may differ across the country. Kasozi (2017) document a positive correlation between the account collection periods (ARP), Account Payment Period (APP) and Inventory Management (IM) and profitability. The study does not include cash conversion cycle, account receivable, account payables and others which variables that could be used to measure working capital management and has a significant influence on firms' profitability.

Zariyawati, Hirnisa and Diana-Rose (2017), research on the effect of working capital management on performance of small and large firms. The research was focused on 24 firms using balance panel data analysis. The study revealed a positive correlation between the cash conversion circle and the performance of small and large firms. The research does not consider other variables for working capital management such as, account payables, inventory holding period, and inventory management. Ukaegbu (2014) report a negative correlation between the cash conversion circle and account collection period and the profitability of firms in Africa. From the foregoing, studies have advanced to consider the component of working capital management on performance but to best of our knowledge, non-have considered commonwealth countries and also long run implication of macroeconomic variable effect on the performance (Asaleye et al., 2022b; Obadiaru et al., 2018). To close this gap in the literature, we examined the long run effect of working capital management component and its effect on performance in African countries within the common wealth nation. And this is important given the low level of output, high unemployment and poverty rate in African economies (Asaleye et al., 2017; Oloni et al., 2017; Popoola et al., 2019).

3. METHOD AND DATA SOURCES

This study employs quantitative research design to investigate the effect of working capital management and financial performance of listed manufacturing companies in selected African countries. The population of the study focuses on African countries that are members of the commonwealth. For the purpose of ensuring uniformity in the classification of consumer goods, the classification based on African financial was used, which are: food and beverages, health services, transport, support services, printing and publishing. The total quoted companies are in food and beverages, health services, transport, support services, printing and publishing in Botswana, Ghana, Kenya, Nigeria, South Africa and Zambia. The sample size for the study consists only of quoted manufacturing firms. It also considers firms that have been listed since 2014 and are still in existence and whose financial reports are accessible for the sample period (2014–2019).

Table 1: Selected companies

Selected Countries	Total Quoted Companies under Manufacturing Companies	Total Selected Companies
Botswana	14	10
Ghana	16	13
Kenya	40	21
Nigeria	83	53
South Africa	50	26
Zambia	18	10

Source: Author's computation (2022) based on information gather from the respective countries' stock exchange

The Model used for this study is stated below;

$$ROE_{it} = f(WCM_{it}, LEV_{it}, ATAN_{it}, GDP_{it}, INT_{it}) \quad 1$$

Model expansions of WCM expressed in mathematical function form are then classified into;

$$ROE_{it} = f(ARP_{it}, LEV_{it}, ATAN_{it}, GDP_{it}, INT_{it}) \quad 2$$

$$ROE_{it} = f(APP_{it}, LEV_{it}, ATAN_{it}, GDP_{it}, INT_{it}) \quad 3$$

$$ROE_{it} = f(INVM_{it}, LEV_{it}, ATAN_{it}, GDP_{it}, INT_{it}) \quad 4$$

$$ROE_{it} = f(CCC_{it}, LEV_{it}, ATAN_{it}, GDP_{it}, INT_{it}) \quad 5$$

Where:

ROE_{it} = Return on Assets

ARP_{it} = Accounts Receivables Period

APP_{it} = Accounts Payment Period

$INVM_{it}$ = Inventory Management

LEV_{it} = Leverage

$ATAN_{it}$ = Assets Turnover

GDP_{it} = Gross Domestic Product

INT_{it} = Interest Rate

α = Intercept

β_1 - β_6 = slope coefficient

E_{it} = Error term

First, we carried out the unit test to confirm the stationary properties of the variables used in this study. Based on the result of the unit root, we proceed to investigate the long-run behaviour with the most appropriate technique using the fully modified least square (Asaleye et al., 2022a)

Table 2: Data Source and Measurement

S/N	Variables Names	Variable Type	Proxy	Formula
1	Return on equity (ROE)	Dependent Variable	Financial Performance	Profit after tax divided by Equities multiply by 100
2	Cash Conversion Cycle (CCC)	Independent Variable	Working Capital Management	Operating Cycle minus Payable Outstanding
3	Accounts Collection Period (ACP)	Independent Variable	Working Capital Management	Debtors divided by Revenue multiplied by the 365 days
4	Accounts Payment Period (APP)	Independent Variable	Working Capital Management	Creditors divided by cost of sales multiplied by 365 days
5	Inventory Management (INVM)	Independent Variable	Working Capital Management	Inventory divided by cost of sales multiplied by 365 days
6	Leverage (LEV)	Control Variable	Leverage	Total debt divided by total assets
7	Assets Turnover (ATAN)	Control Variable	Asset Turnover	Assets divided by Revenue
8	Gross Domestic Product (GDP)	Control Variable	Gross Domestic Product)	Gross domestic product per individual countries
9	Interest Rate (INT)	Control Variable	Interest Rate	Interest rate per individual countries

Source: Author's computation (2022)

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Stationarity Result

Table 3: Stationarity Result

Botswana									
LLC	APP	ARP	ATAN	CCC	GDP	INT	INVM	LEV	ROE
Level	-0.64066	-3.47187 ^c	-5.7973	-0.89482	-18.466 ^c	-0.7845	-4.62831 ^c	-4.62831 ^c	-17.162 ^c
First Df.	-7.8315 ^c	-4.28538 ^c	-7.2392	-5.4776 ^c	-36.691 ^c	-2.4201 ^b	-7.24235 ^c	-7.24235 ^c	-38.701 ^c
BRG									
Level	-2.07458 ^c	0.1524	-5.133 ^c	0.01167	0.45802	-0.30201	1.666	1.66600	0.10062
First Df.	-3.22984 ^c	-2.4333 ^b	-7.9478 ^c	-3.6687 ^b	-2.5132 ^c	-2.5132 ^b	3.66911 ^b	3.66911 ^b	-0.2395 ^b
Ghana									
LLC	APP	ARP	ATAN	CCC	GDP	INT	INVM	LEV	ROE
Level	-2.98310	-15.8818 ^c	-3.3640	-16.253 ^c	-30.6926 ^c	-1.14672	-7.82644 ^c	-20.0940 ^c	-30.661 ^c
First Df.	-16.5866 ^c	-18.4249 ^c	-14.428 ^c	-32.202 ^c	-18.9722 ^c	-16.4480 ^c	-23.1192 ^c	-26.4144 ^c	-53.414 ^c
BRG									
Level	1.65370	1.18500	1.89554	-0.00120	0.65175	-0.45094	-0.01662	0.25940	0.18367
First Df.	0.97294 ^b	3.22246 ^b	-2.6275 ^b	-038023 ^b	-2.72803 ^c	2.77012 ^b	2.31527 ^b	3.12863 ^b	3.41481 ^b
Kenya									
LLC	APP	ARP	ATAN	CCC	GDP	INT	INVM	LEV	ROE
Level	-6.84629 ^c	-4.23599 ^c	-24.441 ^c	-14.067 ^c	-17.1898 ^c	-30.1259 ^c	-13.0019 ^c	-28.2156 ^c	-13.712 ^c
First Df.	-11.1748 ^c	-10.8818 ^c	-46.086 ^c	-17.933 ^c	18.2491 ^c	-32.6334 ^c	-15.7867 ^c	-227.910 ^c	-18.228 ^c
BRG									
Level	1.87017	3.58829	0.29857	1.38011	1.29678	-4.87720	-0.72392	1.45792	3.23987 ^a
First Df.	2.96642 ^b	10.6910 ^c	-3.2449 ^b	2.26874 ^b	12.6726 ^c	-18.7302 ^c	-2.54343 ^b	-2.07183 ^b	5.77955 ^b
Nigeria									
LLC	APP	ARP	ATAN	CCC	GDP	INT	INVM	LEV	ROE
Level	-23.6604 ^c	-30.0912 ^c	-24.766 ^c	-17.453 ^c	7.77073 ^b	-19.9521 ^c	-24.2389 ^c	-14.5214 ^c	-16.673 ^c
First Df.	-46.4201 ^c	-21.9403 ^c	-25.233 ^c	-78.153 ^c	-81.335 ^c	-40.2952 ^c	-67.109 ^c	-22.3413 ^c	-41.048 ^c
BRG									
Level	3.46802 ^a	1.94835	3.29231 ^a	2.6071 ^a	7.1833 ^a	-5.07330 ^a	2.99478 ^a	1.49812	3.7379 ^a
First Df.	5.52253 ^b	6.35602 ^b	5.19114 ^b	2.1388 ^b	-13.1173 ^c	-7.79174 ^c	4.29045 ^c	4.85793 ^b	4.3723 ^b
South Africa									
LLC	APP	ARP	ATAN	CCC	GDP	INT	INVM	LEV	ROE
Level	-24.6770 ^c	-8.90870 ^c	-6.9576 ^c	-10.572 ^c	-6.82587 ^c	-5.32284 ^c	-16.9524 ^c	-3.87523 ^c	-5.6064 ^c
First Df.	-24.2699 ^c	-11.8517 ^c	-11.0986	-14.004 ^c	-10.3118 ^c	-7.55649 ^c	-16.188 ^c	-123.253 ^c	-52.860 ^c
BRG									
Level	-0.66572	1.47600	1.70864	0.49196	-1.66124	-2.35755 ^a	0.03168	2.17535	1.02926
First Df.	3.55333 ^a	-2.72657 ^b	-4.52265	2.92918 ^c	3.24215 ^b	3.10843 ^c	2.52530 ^b	-1.52149 ^a	-2.1111 ^b
Zambia									
LLC	APP	ARP	ATAN	CCC	GDP	INT	INVM	LEV	ROE
Level	-6.37261 ^c	-9.02984 ^c	-9.9432 ^c	-12.952 ^c	-8.67468 ^c	-3.48159 ^c	-7.11610 ^c	-6.99643 ^c	-157.71 ^c
First Df.	-10.7657 ^c	-29.2043 ^c	-21.821 ^c	-15.892 ^c	-9.49988 ^c	-27.1613 ^c	-10.6300 ^c	-31.7858 ^c	-123.95 ^c
BRG									
Level	1.77439	0.12389	0.2381	1.48694	-1.89751 ^a	-1.70213 ^a	0.06510	1.38660	-1.5637 ^a
First Df.	3.27478 ^b	2.69490 ^b	2.66742 ^b	-2.2718 ^b	2.54840 ^b	-4.31135 ^c	2.36206 ^b	2.67533 ^b	-2.1231 ^b
LLC represents Levin, Lin & Chu Unit Root Test/ Null Hypothesis: Unit root (commo unit root process)									
BRG represents Breitung Unit Root/ Null Hypothesis: Unit root (commo unit root process)									

'a' indicates significance @ 10 percent, 'b' and 'c' indicate significance @ 5 percent and 1 percent respectively.

Source: Author's Computation (2022)

The panel unit root test for the six nations is displayed in table 4. This theory is approved utilizing two approaches specifically; Levin, Lin & Chu Unit Root Test and Breitung Unit Root. The tests were carried out at their noteworthiness levels, 10 percent, 5 percent and 1 percent. In any case, assessment of theory was done utilizing 5 percent noteworthiness level.

Prove from table 4 appearing the unit root result portrays that all factors are stationary at level 1 utilizing 5 percent significance level. In Botswana, utilizing Levin, Lin & Chu Unit Root Test (LLC), the factors ARP, GDP, INVM and ROE are stationary at the level form. Whereas utilizing Breitung Unit Root (BRG), ATAN is stationary at the level form. Be that as it may, all factors ended up stationary at integration of order one. In Ghana, the BRG appears that APP and ATAN are stationary at the level form whereas the LLC appears that ARP, CCC, GDP, INT, INVM, LEV and ROE are stationary at the level form. Both the LLC and BRG demonstrate that all the series are stationary at arrange first order in Ghana. Moreover, in Kenya, all arrangement are stationary utilizing LLC whereas none is stationary at the level form utilizing BRG. But all series are stationary at the first differencing form from both unit root tests.

In Nigeria, all the variables are stationary at the level form utilizing the LLC. Whereas BRG, APP, ATAN, CCC, GDP, INT, INVM and ROE are stationary at 10 percent at level form utilizing BRG. In South Africa, all factors are stationary at the level form utilizing LLC whereas INT is stationary at the level utilizing BRG. But all are integrated of order one. In Zambia, all factors are stationary at the level frame utilizing LLC whereas GDP, INT, NPR and ROE are stationary at 10 percent significant level when utilizing BRG. In any case, all series became stationary at first differencing form.

Since all the variable are integrated of order one. Based on the outcome of the unit root test. We employ fully modified OLS to estimate the long-run behaviour.

4.2 Long-run Behaviour Results

Table 4 presents the Panel Fully Modified Least Squares (FMOLS) for Botswana; using the benchmark of significance at 5 per cent, in model 1, ARP and INT are not significant. LEV, ATAN and GDP are significant. LEV, ATAN and GDP have positive relationship with the dependent variable (ROE). This result shows that one percentage in any of the variable by holding other constant will result to an increment of about 1.82 percent, 0.35 percent and 0.46 percent respectively in the dependent variable. In model 2, LEV and INT are not significant. APP, ATAN and GDP are significant. The result shows a positive relationship between the variables (APP, ATAN and GDP) with the dependent variable. Therefore, one percent change in APP, ATAN and GDP will result to about 0.66 percent, 0.35 percent and 0.61percent increase respectively in the dependent variable. In model 3, INVM, LEV and INT are not significant. ATAN and GDP are significant; the result indicates that one percentage change in ATAN and GDP will result to about 0.35 percent reduction in the dependent variable. And about 0.44 percent increase in the GDP. In model 4, LEV and INT are not significant. ATAN and GDP are significant while CCC is significant at the level of 10 percent. ATAN has negative relationship with ROE; indicate that one percentage change in ATAN will lead to about 0.35

percent reduction in ROE. Also, GDP and CCC have positive relationship with ROE; meaning a percentage change in CCC and GDP will lead to about 0.19 percent and 0.40 percent increase in the dependent variable.

Table 4: Panel Fully Modified Least Squares (FMOLS) for Botswana

Dependent Variable: ROE (Model 1)					Dependent Variable: ROE (Model 2)				
Variable	Coeff.	Std. Error	t-Stat.	Prob.	Variable	Coeff.	Std. Error	t-Stat.	Prob.
ARP	-0.13996	0.309812	-0.451755	0.6539	APP	0.661525 ^c	0.151302	4.372204	0.0001
LEV	1.823145 ^b	0.871564	2.091808	0.0416	LEV	0.002280	0.017726	0.128619	0.8983
ATAN	0.35068 ^c	0.009655	36.32173	0.0000	ATAN	0.350190 ^c	0.007581	46.19387	0.0000
GDP	0.459015 ^c	0.142264	3.226499	0.0025	GDP	0.618705 ^c	0.109180	5.666819	0.0000
INT	-0.22297	0.217306	-1.026039	0.3110	INT	-0.193811	0.167661	-1.155966	0.2546
R-squared: 0.877323		S.E. of regression: 0.388761			R-squared: 0.885849		S.E. of regression: 0.307107		
Adjusted R-squared: 0.875055		Long-run variance: 0.172023			Adjusted R-squared: 0.884433		Long-run variance: 0.107520		
Dependent Variable: ROE (Model 3)					Dependent Variable: ROE (Model 4)				
Variable	Coeff.	Std. Error	t-Stat.	Prob.	Variable	Coeff.	Std. Error	t-Stat.	Prob.
INVM	-0.027187	0.121905	-0.223016	0.8247	CCC	0.192049 ^a	0.109849	1.748289	0.0881
LEV	0.014526	0.022372	0.649288	0.5199	LEV	0.005216	0.021925	0.237893	0.8132
ATAN	-0.351076 ^c	0.009613	-36.52149	0.0000	ATAN	-0.352542 ^c	0.009265	-38.05247	0.0000
GDP	0.435924 ^c	0.129819	3.357938	0.0017	GDP	0.402299 ^c	0.123206	3.265240	0.0022
INT	-0.199744	0.212455	-0.940169	0.3528	INT	-0.182423	0.204577	-0.891708	0.3779
R-squared: 0.877211		S.E. of regression: 0.389719			R-squared: 0.879234		S.E. of regression: 0.372020		
Adjusted R-squared: 0.874932		Long-run variance: 0.172423			Adjusted R-squared: 0.877157		Long-run variance: 0.159642		

Source: Authors' computation (2022)

Table 5: Panel Fully Modified Least Squares (FMOLS) for Ghana

Dependent Variable: ROE (Model 1)					Dependent Variable: ROE (Model 2)				
Variable	Coeff.	Std. Error	t-Stat.	Prob.	Variable	Coeff.	Std. Error	t-Stat.	Prob.
ARP	1.413433 ^c	0.131894	10.71645	0.0000	APP	0.002335	0.075613	0.030881	0.9755
LEV	0.380524	0.264700	1.437568	0.1558	LEV	0.582879 ^c	0.033444	-17.42860	0.0000
ATAN	1.427732 ^c	0.122722	11.63383	0.0000	ATAN	1.052240 ^c	0.107849	-9.756566	0.0000
GDP	-0.819743	0.551702	-1.485843	0.1426	GDP	-0.799492	0.509583	-1.568913	0.1219
INT	-1.052765	0.110145	-9.557978	0.0000	INT	1.307430	0.027346	47.81073	0.0000
R-squared: 0.676263		S.E. of regression: 0.618742			R-squared: 0.606614		S.E. of regression: 0.618605		
Adjusted R-squared: 0.603347		Long-run variance: 0.508714			Adjusted R-squared: 0.553722		Long-run variance: 0.435715		
Dependent Variable: ROE (Model 3)					Dependent Variable: ROE (Model 4)				
Variable	Coeff.	Std. Error	t-Stat.	Prob.	Variable	Coeff.	Std. Error	t-Stat.	Prob.
INVM	-0.146946	0.115003	-1.277766	0.2063	CCC	1.070114 ^b	0.521375	2.052484	0.0451
LEV	-0.145540 ^c	0.029339	-4.960621	0.0000	LEV	0.425293 ^a	0.221407	1.920862	0.0601
ATAN	-0.064093 ^b	0.027551	-2.326306	0.0234	ATAN	-0.059006	0.030237	-1.951458	0.0557
GDP	-0.767278	0.505589	-1.517592	0.1344	GDP	1.310537 ^b	0.640065	2.047506	0.0456
INT	1.071159	0.682778	1.568825	0.1219	INT	0.996849	0.737928	1.350877	0.1818
R-squared: 0.693622		S.E. of regression: 0.623649			R-squared: 0.796515		S.E. of regression: 0.622530		
Adjusted R-squared: 0.639864		Long-run variance: 0.427600			Adjusted R-squared: 0.742949		Long-run variance: 0.485653		

Source: Authors' computation (2022)

Table 5 presents the Panel Fully Modified Least Squares (FMOLS) for Ghana; using the benchmark of significance at 5 per cent, in model 1, LEV, GDP and INT are not significant. ARP and ATAN are significant. ARP and ATAN have positive relationship with the dependent variable (ROE). This result shows that one percentage in any of the variable by holding other constant will result to an increment of about 1.41 percent and 1.43 percent respectively in the dependent variable. In model 2, APP, GDP and INT are not significant however, LEV and ATAN are significant. The result shows a positive relationship between the variables (LEV and ATAN) with the dependent variable. Therefore, one percent change in LEV and ATAN will result to about 0.58 percent and 1.05 percent increase respectively in the dependent variable. In model 3, INVM, GDP and INT are not significant. LEV and ATAN are significant; the result indicate that one percentage change in LEV and ATAN will result to about 0.15 percent and 0.06 reductions respectively in the dependent variable. In model 4, ATAN and INT are not significant. CCC, LEV and GDP have positive and significant relationship with ROE;

meaning a percentage change in CCC. LEV and GDP will lead to about 1.07 percent, 0.43 and 1, 31 percent increase in the dependent variable.

Table 6: Panel Fully Modified Least Squares (FMOLS) for Kenya

Dependent Variable: ROE (Model 1)					Dependent Variable: ROE (Model 2)				
Variable	Coeff.	Std. Error	t-Stat.	Prob.	Variable	Coeff.	Std. Error	t-Stat.	Prob.
ARP	0.148075 ^c	0.026670	5.552151	0.0000	APP	1.57E-05	0.000368	0.042664	0.9661
LEV	-0.034802	0.335865	-0.103620	0.9177	LEV	0.151165 ^c	0.027040	5.590517	0.0000
ATAN	0.150435 ^c	0.027777	5.415850	0.0000	ATAN	0.383218 ^c	0.154832	2.475053	0.0164
GDP	-0.081964	0.402389	-0.203694	0.8391	GDP	0.050790	0.469375	0.108207	0.9141
INT	0.297239	0.830504	0.357902	0.7213	INT	0.078954	0.952355	0.082904	0.9341
R-squared: 0.704457		S.E. of regression: 0.545369			R-squared: 0.7501913		S.E. of regression: 0.573690		
Adjusted R-squared: 0.642393		Long-run variance: 0.493663			Adjusted R-squared: 0.7054295		Long-run variance: 0.573704		
Dependent Variable: ROE (Model 3)					Dependent Variable: ROE (Model 4)				
Variable	Coeff.	Std. Error	t-Stat.	Prob.	Variable	Coeff.	Std. Error	t-Stat.	Prob.
INVM	7.87E-06	0.000201	0.039103	0.9689	CCC	0.150636 ^c	0.026608	5.661341	0.0000
LEV	0.151165 ^c	0.027040	5.590517	0.0000	LEV	0.466361 ^b	0.228368	2.042147	0.0459
ATAN	0.391447 ^c	0.144857	2.702308	0.0091	ATAN	-0.067052	0.084707	-0.791580	0.4311
GDP	-0.001295	0.440489	-0.002940	0.9977	GDP	0.148114 ^c	0.027446	5.396636	0.0000
INT	0.156660	0.896784	0.174691	0.8618	INT	0.077073	0.955000	0.080705	0.9359
R-squared: 0.7210192		S.E. of regression: 0.556007			R-squared: 0.6201149		S.E. of regression: 0.573758		
Adjusted R-squared: 0.6049798		Long-run variance: 0.541695			Adjusted R-squared: 0.5954544		Long-run variance: 0.573760		

Source: Authors' computation (2022)

Table 6 presents the Panel Fully Modified Least Squares (FMOLS) for Kenya: Using the benchmark of significance at 5 per cent. In model 1, LEV, GDP and INT are not significant. ARP and ATAN are significance. ARP and ATAN have positive relationship with the dependent variable (ROE). This result shows that one percentage in any of the variable by holding other constant will result to an increment of about 1.48 percent and 0.15 percent respectively in the dependent variable. In model 2, APP, GDP and INT are not significant. LEV and ATAN are significant. The result shows a positive relationship between the variables (LEV and ATAN) with the dependent variable. Therefore, one percent change in LEV and ATAN will result to about 0.15 percent and 0.38 percent increase respectively in the dependent variable. In model 3, INVM, GDP and INT are not significant. LEV and ATAN are significant;

the result indicates that one percentage change in LEV and ATAN will result to about 0.15 percent and 0.39 increase respectively in the dependent variable. In model 4, ATAN and INT are not significant. CCC, LEV and GDP are significant. CCC, LEV and GDP have positive relationship with ROE; meaning a percentage change in CCC, LEV and GDP will lead to about 0.15 percent, 0.47 and 0.15 percent increase in the dependent variable.

Table 7: Panel Fully Modified Least Squares (FMOLS) for Nigeria

Dependent Variable: ROE (Model 1)					Dependent Variable: ROE (Model 2)				
Variable	Coeff.	Std. Error	t-Stat.	Prob.	Variable	Coeff.	Std. Error	t-Stat.	Prob.
ARP	-0.108466	0.076895	-1.410577	0.1595	APP	0.074435 ^b	0.030009	2.480411	0.0137
LEV	0.162340 ^c	0.057156	2.840294	0.0048	LEV	-0.017787	0.010011	-1.776697	0.0767
ATAN	0.021708 ^b	0.009983	-2.174566	0.0305	ATAN	0.179723 ^b	0.082035	2.190815	0.0293
GDP	0.992488 ^b	0.477885	2.076833	0.0410	GDP	0.093260 ^c	0.017837	5.228600	0.0000
INT	0.135605	0.226310	0.599200	0.5495	INT	0.079873	0.228345	0.349789	0.7268
R-squared: 0.699392		S.E. of regression: 0.474714			R-squared: 0.682490		S.E. of regression: 0.479147		
Adjusted R-squared: 0.606526		Long-run variance: 0.334694			Adjusted R-squared: 0.609383		Long-run variance: 0.336108		
Dependent Variable: ROE (Model 3)					Dependent Variable: ROE (Model 4)				
Variable	Coeff.	Std. Error	t-Stat.	Prob.	Variable	Coeff.	Std. Error	t-Stat.	Prob.
INVM	-0.149305	0.077172	-1.934696	0.0540	CCC	-0.095048 ^c	0.017894	-5.311769	0.0000
LEV	0.022856	0.077503	0.294909	0.7683	LEV	-0.086249	0.083262	-1.035882	0.3012
ATAN	0.021054 ^b	0.010089	2.086811	0.0378	ATAN	0.094937 ^c	0.017778	5.340279	0.0000
GDP	0.355992 ^b	0.146386	2.431869	0.0172	GDP	0.330930 ^c	0.021063	15.71108	0.0000
INT	0.125073	0.229319	0.545413	0.5859	INT	0.162750	0.231215	0.703887	0.4821
R-squared: 0.695614		S.E. of regression: 0.475708			R-squared: 0.663781		S.E. of regression: 0.484008		
Adjusted R-squared: 0.582694		Long-run variance: 0.341864			Adjusted R-squared: 0.550406		Long-run variance: 0.347199		

Source: Authors' computation (2022)

Table 7 presents panel fully modified Least Squares (FMOLS) for Nigeria; using the benchmark of significance at 5 per cent. In model 1, ARP and INT are not significant. LEV, ATAN and GDP are significance. LEV, ATAN and GDP have positive relationship with the dependent variable (ROE). This result shows that one percentage in any of the variable by holding other constant will result to an increment of about 0.16 percent, 0.02 percent and 0.99 percent respectively in the dependent variable. In model 2, LEV and INT are not significant. APP, ATAN and GDP are significant. The result shows a positive relationship between the variables (APP, ATAN and GDP) with the dependent variable. Therefore, one percent change

in APP, ATAN and GDP will result to about 0.74 percent, 0.178 percent and 0.09 percent increase respectively in the dependent variable. In model 3, INVM, LEV and INT are not significant. ATAN and GDP are significant; the result indicates that one percentage change in ATAN and GDP will result to about 0.02 percent increase in the dependent variable. And about 0.36 percent increase in the GDP. In model 4, LEV and INT are not significant. CCC, ATAN and GDP are significant. CCC has negative relationship with ROE; indicate that one percentage change in CCC will lead to about 0.1 percent reduction in ROE. Also, ATAN and GDP have positive relationship with ROE; meaning a percentage change in ATAN and GDP will lead to about 0.02 percent and 0.33 percent increase in the dependent variable.

Table 8: Panel Fully Modified Least Squares (FMOLS) for South Africa

Dependent Variable: ROE (Model 1)					Dependent Variable: ROE (Model 2)				
Variable	Coeff.	Std. Error	t-Stat.	Prob.	Variable	Coeff.	Std. Error	t-Stat.	Prob.
ARP	0.335726 ^b	0.151434	2.216982	0.0321	APP	-0.222011	0.172128	-1.289802	0.2045
LEV	-0.161204	0.218164	-0.738912	0.4643	LEV	0.468653 ^c	0.139576	3.357683	0.0017
ATAN	0.129245 ^b	0.062341	2.073194	0.0446	ATAN	0.155499 ^b	0.063895	2.433662	0.0195
GDP	-0.129043	0.206221	-0.625751	0.5350	GDP	-0.079154	0.200729	-0.394333	0.6954
INT	0.668067	0.718084	0.930347	0.3578	INT	0.472148	0.712441	0.662718	0.5113
R-squared: 0.783994		S.E. of regression: 0.381339			R-squared: 0.646613		S.E. of regression: 0.368074		
Adjusted R-squared: 0.707607		Long-run variance: 0.140534			Adjusted R-squared: 0.611274		Long-run variance: 0.134536		
Dependent Variable: ROE (Model 3)					Dependent Variable: ROE (Model 4)				
Variable	Coeff.	Std. Error	t-Stat.	Prob.	Variable	Coeff.	Std. Error	t-Stat.	Prob.
INVM	-0.022941	0.173068	-0.132553	0.8952	CCC	0.329964 ^b	0.149843	2.202063	0.0331
LEV	-0.625842 ^b	0.271632	-2.304004	0.0265	LEV	0.468067 ^c	0.138437	3.381077	0.0015
ATAN	-0.137385 ^c	0.049759	2.761017	0.0087	ATAN	0.117177	0.080495	1.455708	0.1533
GDP	-0.085573	0.183510	-0.466311	0.6435	GDP	1.075292 ^b	0.505415	-2.127540	0.0391
INT	0.529747	0.646587	0.819296	0.4175	INT	0.646554	0.742528	0.870747	0.3891
R-squared: 0.756119		S.E. of regression: 0.343648			R-squared: 0.690849		S.E. of regression: 0.379909		
Adjusted R-squared: 0.681731		Long-run variance: 0.112328			Adjusted R-squared: 0.610366		Long-run variance: 0.146366		

Source: Authors' computation (2022)

Table 8 presents the panel Fully Modified Least Squares (FMOLS) for South Africa. Using the benchmark of significance at 5 per cent. In model 1, LEV, GDP and INT are not significant. ARP and ATAN are significant. ARP and ATAN have positive relationship with the dependent variable (ROE). This result shows that one percentage increase in ARP and ATAN, and holding

other constant will result to an increment of about 0.33 percent and 0.13 percent respectively in the dependent variable. In model 2, APP, GDP and INT are not significant. LEV and ATAN are significant. The result shows a positive relationship between the variables (LEV and ATAN) with the dependent variable. Therefore, one percent change in LEV and ATAN will result to about 0.47 percent and 0.16 percent increase respectively in the dependent variable. In model 3, INVM, GDP and INT are not significant. LEV and ATAN are significant; the result indicates that one percentage change in LEV and ATAN will result to about 0.62 percent and 0.14 reductions respectively in the dependent variable. In model 4, ATAN and INT are not significant. CCC, LEV and GDP are significant. CCC, LEV and GDP have positive relationship with ROE; meaning a percentage change in CCC, LEV and GDP will lead to about 0.33 percent, 0.47 and 1.08 percent increase in the dependent variable.

Table 9: Panel Fully Modified Least Squares (FMOLS) for Zambia

Dependent Variable: ROE (Model 1)					Dependent Variable: ROE (Model 2)				
Variable	Coeff.	Std. Error	t-Stat.	Prob.	Variable	Coeff.	Std. Error	t-Stat.	Prob.
ARP	0.732461 ^b	0.310394	2.359776	0.0227	APP	0.004197	0.058339	0.071936	0.9430
LEV	-1.181830	0.768757	-1.537325	0.1312	LEV	1.427237 ^b	0.638018	2.703111	0.0463
ATAN	0.085564 ^c	0.028185	3.035779	0.0040	ATAN	0.084759 ^c	0.030643	2.766071	0.0085
GDP	-0.043541	0.080041	-0.543985	0.5891	GDP	0.665995 ^a	0.345595	1.927097	0.0611
INT	-0.397292	0.648990	-0.612170	0.5435	INT	-0.102221	0.743039	-0.137572	0.8913
R-squared: 0.786928		S.E. of regression: 0.924103			R-squared: 0.709074		S.E. of regression: 0.927100		
Adjusted R-squared: 0.714655		Long-run variance: 0.748346			Adjusted R-squared: 0.699982		Long-run variance: 0.873315		
Dependent Variable: ROE (Model 3)					Dependent Variable: ROE (Model 4)				
Variable	Coeff.	Std. Error	t-Stat.	Prob.	Variable	Coeff.	Std. Error	t-Stat.	Prob.
INVM	0.355614	0.604953	0.587837	0.5599	CCC	0.085109 ^c	0.030527	2.788025	0.0081
LEV	1.628471 ^b	0.771194	2.469240	0.0489	LEV	0.057433 ^b	0.023522	2.441692	0.0180
ATAN	0.082834 ^c	0.030602	2.706801	0.0099	ATAN	-0.023961	0.077374	-0.309684	0.7584
GDP	0.601208	0.357727	1.680637	0.1006	GDP	0.299656 ^b	0.138628	2.161593	0.0352
INT	-0.029921	0.743257	-0.040257	0.9681	INT	-0.102059	0.738603	-0.138179	0.8908
R-squared: 0.616368		S.E. of regression: 0.922816			R-squared: 0.609543		S.E. of regression: 0.926826		
Adjusted R-squared: 0.538005		Long-run variance: 0.864332			Adjusted R-squared: 0.590497		Long-run variance: 0.866448		

Source: Authors' computation (2022)

Table 9 presents the panel fully modified least squares (FMOLS) for Zambia. Using the benchmark of significance at 5 per cent. In model 1, LEV, GDP and INT are not significant. ARP and ATAN are significant. ARP and ATAN have positive relationship with the dependent

variable (ROE). This result shows that one percentage increase in either ARP or ATAN and holding other constant will result to an increment of about 0.73 percent and 0.09 percent respectively in the dependent variable. In model 2, APP and INT are not significant. GDP is significant at the level of 10 percent. LEV and ATAN are significant. The result shows a positive relationship between the variables (LEV and ATAN) with the dependent variable. Therefore, one percent change in LEV and ATAN will result to about 1.43 percent and 0.08 percent increase respectively in the dependent variable. In model 3, INVM, GDP and INT are not significant. LEV and ATAN are significant; the result indicates that one percentage change in LEV and ATAN will result to about 1.63 percent and 0.08 per cent increase respectively in the dependent variable. In model 4, ATAN and INT are not significant. CCC, LEV and GDP are significant. CCC, LEV and GDP have positive relationship with ROE; meaning a percentage change in CCC. LEV and GDP will lead to about 0.09 percent, 0.06 and 0.3 percent increase in the dependent variable.

5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Based on the research, the study concludes as follows; various countries have various working capital management practices; account receivables period has negative but insignificant relationship with return on equity; account payment period has positive and significant relationship with ROE; inventory management has negative but insignificant relationship with return on equity and cash conversion cycle has positive and insignificant relationship with performance measured with return on equity. In line with the findings, the followings recommendations were made; Ghana, Kenya, South Africa and Zambia needs to increase receivables period for purpose of improving financial performance while Botswana and Nigeria, account receivables need not to be delayed for the purpose of improving financial performance; delay in payment period for Botswana, Ghana, Kenya, Nigeria and Zambia since it is negatively correlated to financial performance but early payment period in South Africa since has negative correlation to financial performance; Companies need to manage their inventory level for the purpose of improving financial performance through cost reduction such as holding cost; management of firms needs to focus on cash conversion cycle since it serve as measurement of liquidity by considering time dimension.

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